

Deliverable 2.3

Workpackage WP2-T2

Responsible Partners : INRAe and IP

Contributing partners: ISS, RIVM, IP, IZSLER, IZSAM, ANSES, INRAe, WBVR, UCM, PIWET, DTU, SSI, SVA, SLV

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

WP2-TASK 2 : GAP ANALYSIS OF THE RESOURCES

During the interim meeting held in early February, we have defined the compulsory and desirable criteria for RM strains, yielded a decision tree (see below) for the choice and set up expert groups with one person (indicated in bold) responsible per species :

- *Salmonella* **Henk Aarts**, Benoît Doublet, Anne Brisabois
- *Listeria monocytogenes* **Anne Brisabois**, Sophie Roussel
- *Campylobacter* **Hanna Skarin**, Kees Veldman, Susanne Karlsmose-Pedersen
- Diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* **Valeria Michelacci**, Stefano Morabito, Benoît Doublet
- *Staphylococcus aureus* **Olivier Chesneau**, Maria Ugarte-Ruiz
- *Bacillus cereus* **Nalini Rama Rao**, Olivier Chesneau
- *Yersinia enterocolitica* **Maria Ugarte-Ruiz**, Olivier Chesneau

Decision tree for the choice of RM

